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Music as a Tool for Ethics

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Abstract

The current musical situation nowadays reflects a fast-technological change that has contributed to main social issues, such as a tangible crisis of values globally. The impact of music lyrics, nevertheless, could be a powerful useful tool to engage people in different ethical values leading to an improvement of relationships of any nature. Can music be that magic wand? This study aims at measuring the impact of lyrics on values of people and the power to improve norm activation. A questionnaire based on the Likert scale was conducted among 281 subjects either at university or with university studies. Results were analysed using the structural equation model-partial least square (SEM-PLS), which showed the relevance of items and connected hypotheses and a significant prediction capacity ($R^2 = 0.458$). Conclusions exposed that music can predict attitude change and become a tool for ethics.

Keywords: behaviour; ethics; music; lyrics

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1. Introduction

Facts speak for themselves and music being one of the preferred leisure activities is a fact in today's world. Everywhere we go, music is always there being combined with any situation. Music facilitates suitable environments to engage individuals in universal ethical values (Nicolás & Azorín, 2013), leading, no doubt, to the improvement of relationships.

Regarding emotional states (Hariri, Bookheimer, & Mazziotta, 2000) the connection between values involving emotions to be developed and music arising and representing emotions is undeniable. Ethical values of people positively will be reflected in the way they act and behave on both personal and social levels, since personal beliefs dictate moral obligation (Schwartz & Howard, 1981) and successive norm activation (Liere & Dunlap, 2006). As mentioned before, the global crisis people are currently experiencing (Sorthaix, Parker, Lechner, & Schwartz, 2017) and the fact that music is powerful enough to portray moods and feelings lead us to the hope that music could be the ideal tool for ethical purposes.

Music can be used to *pump* values of all sorts to people and subsequently promote attitude change as lyrics offer the perfect scenario for mostly reflection and feelings (Christenson & Roberts, 1998). It is well-known that lyrics mirror social trends, personal perceptions of life, worries or concerns (Christenson, de Haan-Rietdijk, Roberts, & Bogt, 2019) and have an impact on listeners.

On a wider note, music in a foreign language could serve different purposes, not only to channel emotions and build values but also to improve skills on a more academic level. Schumann (1994) coined social distance as a factor easily found in society that contributes to the learning of a language. Besides, McLean (1980, p.18) stated "a clear need for the content of language-teaching materials to involve the learner -to relate to his needs, interests and moral concerns", therefore the potential of music in English may not be ignored.

Music as a perception and value changer can not only amuse individuals but also increase quality of life (Juslin, Liljeström, Västfjäll, & Lundqvist, 2010) and subsequent attitudes. All in all, music can be proposed as a valuable tool that can improve quality of life.

2. Literature review

Considered a constant factor around us, music can be employed for the promotion of ethics and attitude change, which may definitely lead to an enhanced world where personal as well as social respects is a must, not forgetting nature and the environment (Dietz, Stern, & Rycroft, 1989). The change to use music for prosocial advantages cannot be missed but take advantage; and delving into lyrics and the message they send needs to be considered to achieve meaningful changes in society.

2.1 Music with Personal Values (MPV)

Creativity provided by music is one main factor to consider (Hallam, 2015), since it triggers communication and realiation of own concerns and achievement (DeWall, Pond, Campbell, & Twenge, 2011). Lyrics, no doubt, may lay the floor for personal reflection and therefore reinforce values that set robust behavioural standards in any situation or context (Maslow, 1954; Perrinjaquet, Furrer, Marguerat, Usunier, & Cestre, 2007). When music with self-care values takes over, it definitely improves guidance in life and help overcome personal issues as well as provide gratification (De la Rosa Herrera & Publiese, 2017), which may have an impact on social feelings and skills due to the connection individuals feel when they listen to music, thus becoming one and sharing identity patterns.

Humans are in a constant search for discovering and developing own abilities and potential in order to match their self-concept, image and self-esteem (Rokeach, 1973). On the other hand, music can actually change perceptions and provide meaning to experiences, making them last in time and making them transcend by means of values (Rokeach, 1973; Schwartz, 1994). Music may reflect types of personality and provide benefits such as cognitive, physical or motor skills which can suddenly improve our response drive and act in a specific way (Aubrey, 2006; Schellenberg & von Scheve, 2012), therefore influencing human attitudes.

The statement above leads to Hypothesis 1: Music with Personal Values influence (MPV) have an impact on Actions of People (AP).

2.2 Music with Family/Transcendental Values (MFTV)

It is a fact that songs can actually acquire the role of communicators and disseminators of messages with values since they express ideas and feelings connected to different lyrics and rhythms. Family being the first social group is the promoter of values that are intimately connected to personal experiences and circumstances (Hallam, 2015). Songs are also part of family celebrations which are linked to values that will endure through a life time (Ilisko & Kravale-Paulina, 2015).

A well-known fact is that social bonding is primarily created by music lyrics, which drive individuals to behave in a particular way, enhancing prosocial behaviour (Greitemeyer, 2009a; Greitemeyer, 2009b; Gentile, Anderson, Yukawa, Ithori, Saleem, Ming, & Sakamoto, 2009). Besides, learning processes are facilitated by listening to music, which in turn, will help make decisions on both personal and social levels, since it functions as a promoter of acceptance, tolerance and justice, among others (Hallam, 2015). In addition, transcendental music do have the potential for engagement regarding idealism, divinity or/and individualism (Jackson, 2014), therefore influencing actions of people.

The statement above leads Hypothesis 2: Music with Family and Transcendental values (MFTV) have a positive impact on Actions of People (AP).

2.3 Music with Environmental Values (MEV)

Music being considered as a very powerful means for the dissemination of thoughts, ideas or concerns may actually contribute to the preservation of the environment and everything surrounding environmental issues. Environmental lyrics may not be undermined but the opposite. Music can help spread very different and powerful message depending on musical tastes (Zillmann & Gan, 1997).

On the other hand, lyrics containing ethical messages offer personal as well as social interaction resulting in the enhancement of values related to the environment (Sagiv, Roccas, Ciecuch, & Schwartz, 2017) since they create that special connection and empathy with the world around us. Songs being short and repetitive help with efficiency when it comes to disseminate

messages to others and may have a direct impact feelings and emotions (Taruffi & Koelsch, 2014), influencing behaviour change.

The above information leads to Hypothesis 3: Music with Environmental Values (LEV) have a positive impact on Behaviour Change (BC).

2.4 Social Distance (SD)

The use of the English language has touched every corner of the world and, needless to say, every field of knowledge, consequently learning English has become a *must*; there is always a reason to learn it. According to Kachru and Nelson (2001), English is the language that is internationally being taught and learnt at all levels (González Davies & Celaya Villanueva, 1992; Alcaraz Varó, 2000; Flowerdew & Peacock, 2001) and which is necessary to achieve success, therefore, it plays a main role as a *lingua franca* (Graddol, 1997). Many a country, including Spain, includes English as a second language in their educational system, in their curriculum, therefore it is learnt as a foreign language (González Davies & Celaya Villanueva, 1992); and recently group learning is in high demand as a resource for second language learning processes (Adiantika & Purnomo, 2018).

Due to the era of globalisation we are experiencing, the concept of acculturation comes along; it is a concept involving adjustment/modification of norms established by society, that is, social norms, attitudes and values embraced by a particular culture (Sam & Berry, 2010). To have control of a language somehow portrays more sociability (Albino, 2017). Thus, the social distance phenomenon develops from the cognitive and affective approach when two different cultures come in contact with each other and individuals start to adapt to the new culture by different reasons (emigration, work, learning, acceptance). On a global level, the enormous influence that English music has all over the world is a fact the same as the fact that it is an engaging tool related to learning processes of all kinds (Sánchez González, 2021).

Acquiring a new language may bring unexpected benefits from structural and motivational properties that music has (Fonseca-Mora, Toscano-Fuentes, & Wermke, 2011). Music as a potential instrument for learning, if combined with social distance may positively influence performance of different nature (Sánchez González, 2021).

McLean (1980, p. 17) states that, “Learning is most effective when the learner is the initiator of the learning process”. Since listening to music is such a pleasurable activity that can be employed for many a purpose, individuals, with no much effort, become learners of the message in the lyrics and those lyrics may have an impact on their attitude and actions afterwards (Sánchez González, 2021).

The statements above lead to Hypothesis 4: Social Distance (SD) has a positive impact on Actions of People (AP).

2.5 Actions of People (AP)

Schwartz and Howard (1981) detailed that beliefs of personal nature did imply moral obligations in order to carry out actions to basically avoid consequences that are unwanted. To be aware of those consequences drives the individual to act from a responsible angle in order to obtain established objectives (Han, 2014; Schwartz, 1977).

Actually, emotions have the power to positively activate a wide range of experiences and attitude change in people (Sánchez González, 2021) of all ages, especially in those moments when personality swings do take place (Coyne, Stockdale, Nelson, & Fraser, 2011). When people are wrapped up in music, this fact generates emotions, something innate to humans, acting as a common channel for communication, togetherness (Sanchez González, 2021) and, of course, understanding and respect for the world and all its elements surrounding us. Compromise, then, is born to then promote change in actions and attitudes of people leading to the development of personal rules (Sánchez González, 2021).

The information above leads to Hypothesis 5: Actions of People (AP) have a positive impact on the Development of Personal Rules (DPR).

2.6 Behavioural Changes (BC)

Socialisation is paramount for the survival of the human race. Paying attention to the general learning model, the impact and effects of songs with different lyrics can play a relevant role in social behaviour (Greitemeyer, 2009b). Music is an indispensable element, increasingly being used

in the education of children (Do & Schallert, 2004; Fonseca-Mora, 2000) for reinforcement and enhancement of positive attitudes.

The openness of young people to give anything a chance is something praiseworthy; being open to change also involves adopting the role of collaborators of the world. Although people generally act upon rules learnt from family and personal experiences, to be open to change also affects norm activation (De Groot & Steg, 2009) and this fact may influence other peers.

This statement leads to Hypothesis 6: The Development of Personal Rules (DPR) has a positive impact on Behaviour Change (BC).

2.7 Music as a Tool for Ethics (MTE)

Music is a pleasurable activity able to relax and bring back memories from any time in the past; it has the ability to bond people, not only friends and family members but also any individual that shares the same kind of music; it fetches a sense of identity and belonging (Bogt, Mulder, Raaijmakers, & Gabhainn, 2011) within a joyful atmosphere. It can be said that music with prosocial lyrics can actually influence prosocial behaviour (Greitemeyer, 2009a) as well as personal and social interaction (Sagiv et al., 2017), which may change the world for the better. Al Kandari & Al Qattan (2020) state that task-based learning along with new technologies can effectively influence group learning. Music can be measured as an extremely significant and persuasive instrument that can engage people in different scenarios and therefore enhance values related to personal, environmental, family and transcendental values. Then, the statement that music is a tool for ethics can be affirmed.

These statements then lead to Hypothesis 7: Behaviour Change (BC) has a positive impact on the understanding of Music as a Tool for Ethics (MTE)

Figure 1. Hypotheses according to PLS path modeling

3. Methodology

The methodology of this study is based on main pillars taken from the literature review previously exposed, which leads to the following research question: Can music be a tool for ethics?

In order to write and develop a report on how music and the words of the lyrics can engage with people and change their attitude for then to become an ethical tool for different purposes and as to facilitate the researcher with the capacity for prediction of the fact in consideration (Creswell & Clark, 2017), the quantitative research method was chosen to also meet the aim of this study. This method was believed to be the most suitable considering the population sample being relatively small.

The methodology followed some phases: Phase 1 covered a thorough online search for a wide range of song lyrics containing values that would meet the purpose of the study to then analyse them at a later date. Phase 2 was performed at different universities. Volunteers took part after a brief introduction of the topic by lecturers who collaborated with the researcher. A focus groups had been previously arranged to analyse the questions of the questionnaire to be completed by the students. All participants were of legal age and therefore no ethical considerations were needed to be addressed. In phase 3, a pilot survey was conducted with the intention to double check the level of understanding of the questions and the reliability of possible responses. After some changes, the questions became clearer and shorter with a simplistic design, as suggested by Hoinville and Jowell (1978), as to allocate contents and safeguard top cooperation.

The questionnaire was built upon the Likert-scale model, using multiple-choice answers with a total of with thirty-five (35) items. Participants would take an average time of 4 minutes to complete the questionnaire. After gathering all answers, the analysis thereof followed by using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method (IT program).

3.1 Variable definition

The variables use in this research were justified by the literature review previously stated (See table 1). Every construct of the study was defined by five (5) items acting as measurement models.

Table 1. *Variables justification*

Constructs	Indicators
MPV: Music with Personal Values	<p>MPV 1: Modification in personal values in the socialisation process. (Schwartz, 2011; Rokeach, 1973)</p> <p>MPV 2: Value predilection affects affect different values for attitude change. (Rokeach, 1973; Tooby & Cosmides, 1990)</p> <p>MPV 3: Motivation as vital in efficient learning. (Fonseca-Mora et al., 2011)</p> <p>MPV 4: Fondness and and emotions leading to value development. (Perrinjaquet et al., 2007)</p> <p>MPV 5: Music connected to personality kinds. (Aubrey, 2006; Schellenberg & von Scheve, 2012)</p>
MFTV: Music with Family/Transcendental Values	<p>MFTV 1: Language input, learning to cause attitude change. (Schäfer et al., 2013)</p> <p>MFTV 2: Music, a bond for education. (Do & Schallert, 2004; Fonseca et al., 2011)</p> <p>MFTV 3: Value reinforcement by emotions. (Jackson, 2014)</p> <p>MFTV 4: Music to increase prosocial behaviour. (Greitemeyer, 2009a; Greitemeyer, 2009b; Gentile et al., 2009)</p> <p>MFTV 5: Family values as guiding values. (Ilisko & Kravale-Paulina, 2015)</p>
MEV: Music with Environmental Values	<p>MEV1: Environmental doings to sponsor positive values. (Gatersleben et al., 2008)</p> <p>LEV2: Music, shared ground for creativities. (Gatersleben et al., 2008)</p> <p>MEV3: Cohesion to be boosted by music. (Kachru & Nelson, 2001; Gatersleben et al., 2008)</p> <p>MEV4: Social bonding by emotions provoked (Juslin et al., 2010).</p> <p>MEV5: Social awareness/altruism by values. (Juslin et al., 2010).</p>
SD: Social Distance	<p>SD1: Social distance to drive learning and togetherness. (Sam & Berry, 2010; Schumann, 1994)</p> <p>SD2: English as part of the globalisation process. (Graddol, 1997; Alcaraz Varó, 2000)</p> <p>SD3: A related factor for own learning (Schumann,1994; McLean, 1980)</p>
AP: Actions of People	<p>AP1: Music to relax. (Napier & Shamir, 2018)</p> <p>AP2: Music to motivate. (Christenson et al., 2019)</p> <p>AP3: Music, always suitable (Jackson, 2014).</p> <p>AP4: Music to create (Schellenberg & von Scheve, 2012)</p> <p>AP5: Music to lay ground for reflection (Rentfrow & Gosling, 2003)</p>
DPR: Development of Personal Rules	

	DPR1: Sense of identity, relaxation and belonging by music. (Rentfrow & Gosling, 2003; Napier & Shamir, 2018)
	DSCR2: Connection of people leading to attitude change. (Sortheix et al., 2017)
	DPR3: The omnipresence of music to drive emotions (Taruffi & Koelsch, 2014)
	DSCR4: Music encouraging creativity. (Schellenberg & von Scheve, 2012)
	DPR5: Music to reflect on social values. (Sortheix et al., 2017)
BC: Behaviour Change	BC1: Emotions leading to attitude change. (Rokeach, 1973)
	BC2: Music, common ground for identity (Bogt et al., 2011)
	BC3: Music always suiting a purpose. (Gardner & Lambert, 1972)
MTE: Music as a Tool for Ethics	MTE1: Music as an inspiring tool for mental processes (Fonseca-Mora, 2000)
	MTE2: Music to connect individuals with shared interests. (Sagiv et al., 2017)
	MTE3: Emotions, imperative in attitude change. (Taruffi & Koelsch, 2014)
	MTE4: Actions and awareness (Schwartz, 1977)
	MTEEYP5: Music to connect and spread messages. (Liere & Dunlap, 2006)

3.2 Research population

The participants of the study were mostly university students or subjects with university experience of any kind and branch, since they were considered the most appropriate subjects as they were directly connected with the problem of study and were mature enough to answer with honesty and veracity to the questions given to them. They shared their views about the influence of music in their lives and predicted future changes in behaviour. A total of two hundred and eighty-one (281) participants took part in survey within a period of two to three months in Autumn of 2020.

The research method chosen allowed the collection of data to be easy and cost-effective, as most of the phases were conducted through internet applications and tools such as google forms and instant message available options.

3.3 Data analysis and statistical treatment

The method for data analysis and statistical treatment used was the SmartPLS programme (Ringle, Wende, & Becker, 2015) which made use of the PLS multivariate technique (structural equation modeling) to detect and analyse the relations amongst the variables employed in the study, either unobservable or latent (Hair et al., 2013). Structural Equation Modeling was chosen in order to quantify behavioural patterns for later statistical treatment (Fornell & Bookstein, 1982). It is a model suitable for proposals related to social sciences and to deeply test the hypotheses of the anticipated model.

3.4 Data analysis and measurement model

The main objective of PLS is to predict the dependent variables in order to maximise the explained variance (R^2) that belongs to the dependent variables. In other words, the PLS model (Barclay, Thompson, & Higgins, 1995) encompasses assessment and reliability factors of the measurement model and assessment of the structural model in order to measure and monitor the weight and extend of relations between the variables in the study. To assess both the validity and reliability of the model employed, consistency reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity parameters were used.

As anticipated by Carmines and Zeller (1979), in order to secure indicators, these should have a load equal or above 0.707, that is, the variance that a construct and its indicator share should be higher than the error variance. In this particular case, all loads (λ) were above 0.7, therefore the analysis thereof is then proper and accepted. All outer loadings showed reasonable reliability.

Table 2 displays the construct reliability and convergent validity figures, conducted in order to guarantee internal consistency of the indicators in regards to the construct. This was measured by the Cronbach's Alpha, which states that all figures should be about 0.70, also by the ρA^2 , by the Composite Reliability (CR), with a measure range of 0.70 as well; the convergent validity of the latent variables was assessed by the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Convergent validity reflects the level of correlation between two measures of the same concept. On the other

hand, latent variables should always stay above 0.50 as to properly defend half of the variance of its indicators (Henseler, Ringle, & Sinkovics, 2009). This condition is present in this study.

Constructs have an AVE fluctuating from 0.596 to 0.683 (Table 2), approving that the measurement model has appropriate convergent validity. In regards to internal consistency reliability, the composite reliability (CR) of each construct surpasses the value of 0.7 therefore the consistency is justified.

Table 2. Construct reliability and convergent validity

	Cronbach's alpha¹	rho_A²	Composite reliability (CR)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
AP	0.714	0.715	0.895	0.635
BC	0.764	0.809	0.898	0.638
DPR	0.830	0.865	0.876	0.619
MEV	0.723	0.766	0.855	0.518
MFTV	0.720	0.713	0.817	0.541
MPV	0.811	0.820	0.860	0.617
MTE	0.716	0.743	0.818	0.596
SD	0.764	0.847	0.880	0.683

The assessment of convergent validity is performed by the mean extracted variance (AVE), a measure proposed by Fornell and Larcker (1981), which shows the variance obtained by a construct from its indicator in relation to the variance due to the measurement error. Table 3 shows how following the Fornell-Larcker's criterion, a latent variable is required to share more variance with its indicators than with other variables (Fornell & Bookstein, 1982). Values in the study fulfill this requirement.

Table 3. *Fornell-Larcker criterion*³

	AP	BC	DPR	MEV	MFTV	MPV	MTE	SD
AP	0.813							
BC	0.325	0.839						
DPR	0.540	0.335	0.790					
MEV	0.487	0.437	0.462	0.783				
MFTV	0.568	0.520	0.576	0.687	0.772			
MPV	0.588	0.486	0.542	0.585	0.768	0.782		
MTE	0.625	0.388	0.545	0.510	0.560	0.522	0.762	
SD	0.439	0.373	0.418	0.358	0.401	0.495	0.364	0.842

The last step to take was regarding discriminant validity, which was taken into account in order to validate the measurement scale used in the study and hence define an improved approach of the scale in question. Discriminant validity measure how each and every variable differs from the others. In the Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) factor, measures are far from related. This factor should never go higher than 1 to show accuracy in the distinction between two factors the HTMT value should never exceed 0.90 for the constructs to show correlation and be significative. All results obtained from the model showed a ration below 0.90 (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015).

3.6 Data analysis and inner model

Table 4 shows values corroborating the variance explained (R^2) and results prove the strong connection among the constructs used. As stated by Chin (1998), the coefficient of determination (R^2) can be classified into different categories, those being weak (0.19), modest (0.33) or significant (0.67) depending on the results from variables. This main figure clearly shows how the dependent variable, Music as a Tool for Ethics (MTE) had predictive capacity by showing $R^2 = 0.458$ ($> 0.33 =$ modest). The model used the bootstrapping measuring technique to generate t-statistic values by processing 5,000 random samples from 281 responses obtained.

The Stone–Geisser (Q^2) test (Stone, 1974; Geisser, 1974) states that values can be classified as follows: 0.02 for small, 0.15 for intermediate and 0.35 for pertinent predictive relevance. In this research, all constructs showed that prediction and relevance, as Q^2 values showed 0.02 or above. There is actually relevance prediction if $Q^2 > 0$, which is the case in the

present study, whose dependent variable *Music as a tool for Ethics* (MTE) has proven to have predictive weight (0.248). Table 4 shows constructs confirm that requirement.

Table 4. R^2 = Coefficient determination) and Q^2 = Stone-Geisser test

	R^2	Adjusted R^2	Q^2
AP	0.439	0.431	0.257
BC	0.099	0.096	0.053
DPR	0.291	0.298	0.176
MTE	0.458	0.453	0.248

In order for path coefficients to be validated and be reliable, they should remain above 0.100 in order to create power in the model employed. The structural model proves to be reliable and satisfactory. As Huber et al (2007) corroborate, figures exceeding 0.05 (Huber et al., 2007) are to be suitable and valid.

Taking a look at table 5, confidence intervals as well as t-values are evidenced to deliver the evaluation of the path coefficient. After the analysis of every interval, to obtain 0 is not possible. On the other hand, the worth and weight of the latent variables is to be measured by path coefficients after analysis their relations. This figure should always remain above 0.2 to be suitable. For this study, an additional technique was employed, that is, bootstrapping, in order to estimate the suitability of PLS and calculate standards errors of parametres. (in this precise case, 5,000 samples were used).

Table 5. Confidence intervals

	Original sample (O)	Average sample (M)	2.5%	97.5%
AP -> BC	0.325	0.326	0.225	0.399
AP -> DPR	0.540	0.539	0.419	0.633
AP -> MTE	0.456	0.447	0.344	0.543
BC -> MTE	0.160	0.164	0.072	0.272
DPR -> MTE	0.270	0.269	0.165	0.372
MEV -> AP	0.138	0.175	0.005	0.259
MFTV -> AP	0.213	0.221	0.042	0.362
MPV -> AP	0.281	0.297	0.087	0.423
SD -> AP	0.160	0.177	0.041	0.329

Every construct was proven to be suitable as well as indicators established, which were duly interrelated. The model of variables and hypotheses was exposed and analysed according to the PLS path modeling which predicts the suitability of the constructs (Hair et al., 2014). Regarding the external variables, Music with Personal Values (MPV), Music with Family/Transcendental Values (MFTV), Music with Environmental Values (MEV), Social Distance (SD), Actions of People (AP), Development of Personal Rules (DPR) and Behaviour Change (BC) do actually and definitely converge into the internal variable, Music as a Tool for Ethics (MTE).

Endnotes

- ¹ Ought to exceed 0.70 for individual reliability (Nunnally, 1994).
- ² Ought to exceed 0.70 for individual reliability (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015).
- ³ Values ought to exceed 0.50 to evaluate shared variance between CR & AVE (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Henseler et al., 2015).

4. Discussion and Conclusions

This research analyses and assessed the influence and prediction capacity of music and its intimate connection with ethics and engagement with people. After analysing 281 replies, a model was implemented to demonstrate how music could become a tool by connecting all variables of the model introduced to predict attitude change.

By means of participative methodology and the model built, the constructs proved to have explanatory capacity ($R^2 = 0.458$) to show the relevant power of music, which is a tool to build emotions and reinforce ethics towards society and ourselves.

Firstly, all outer loadings were validated as they showed ($\lambda > 0.7$) for relevance. In addition, all constructs showed pertinent capacity ($R^2 = 0.458$). Regarding confidence intervals (2.5% and 97.5%) these confirm robust relations in variance in all constructs of the model. The predictive capacity Music as a Tool for Ethics (MTE), the dependent variable, must be taken into account ($Q^2 = 0.248$) as it fuses expected results. Also, Actions of People (AP) demonstrated better attitude towards behaviour change, towards personal, family, transcendental and environmental values. Therefore, all hypotheses met the main aim of this research.

The findings of this research coincide with those mentioned in the literature review which state that young people are music bond to such stage that social changes do actually take place and therefore these affect emotions and ethical values. The reliability provided by the model used show accurate responses in a way, confirming that music can actually influence different situations in the life of people, impacting on their ethics.

The results presented how music can transform perceptions and promote attitude change in people. The following conclusions may be drawn:

1. Responses obtained allowed the researcher to quantify social impact due the predicted attitude change after analysis.

2. Being exposed to music with values may enhance emotions leading to attitude change on personal and social levels.

3. The Social Distance (SD) hypothesis proved to have a positive impact on Actions of People (AP), leading to Behaviour Change (BC), and therefore determining that languages come with social beliefs that can be shared with music.

4. The engagement provided by music results in positive responses from those listening to music with ethics in the lyrics.

5. Music can improve and change perceptions of issues in the world promoting behavior change and norm activation.

6. The significant level of acceptance of music as a consistent powerful instrument by those taking part in the questionnaire can help formulate strategies in various academic fields.

7. The model proposed offers a wide range of possibilities related to pedagogy strategies based on ethics connected and applied to subjects in any educational system.

8. Music with Personal Values (MPV), Music with Family/Transcendental Values (MFTV) and Music with Environmental Values (LEV), including the Social Distance (SD) factor, have a positive impact on Actions of People (AP), leading to the Development of Personal Rules (DPR) and affecting Behaviour Change (BC), therefore, the fact that Music can be a Tool for Ethics (MTE) can be confirmed.

This research can be ended by posing the following question: Can music be used for Ethics and become an effective tool? Certainly, it can.

Theoretical and practical implications

As a theoretical implication, this research can be considered an instrument to corroborate past work carried out using same or similar variables, namely, music, youngsters and ethics. As a practical implication, it needs to be mentioned that awareness created in all the parties involved in the study is the main factor, however it could be of interest for any other branch of knowledge, as the variables used are general variables that come be intrinsic to human beings, therefore it would offer transcendence for some problems of practical nature: English music could be used in any educational system and age along with the ethics subject as it would improve not only language skills but also values to deal with any situation in life and make you feel good.

Limitations

The limitations found in this study are related to personal self-belief values as a parental approach has been used all throughout. Besides, intangibles as hypotheses are used and prediction levels are to be seen in the future. In addition, the location where the study was carried out was based solely in Spain.

Recommendations for future research

It would be recommended for future research to delve into different social and linguistics fields that deal with the use of profanity in music and the different paths and impact that this may have on young people and their behavior when dealing with ethical values.

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102